

IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM IN FOOD INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *In the article, the topic of the management methodology of the organizational and economic mechanism of the enterprise during the integration process is highlighted. Mainly, today's food industry enterprises are taken as an object.*

Keywords: *integration, organizational-economic mechanism, innovative technologies, product quality, specialization, capacity, management system, modern method and method.*

In the conditions of today's market relations, food industry enterprises are required to pay great attention to organizational and economic processes such as applying new innovative technologies, increasing product quality, and improving the labor potential of employees. The organization of organizational and economic processes in an optimal form has a great impact on the increase in the volume of production of food industry products.

China, India, the USA and Brazil are the countries that produce the most food products in the world, and these countries are also among the top five in the world in terms of geographical area.

China and India are also major food producing countries, which mainly focus on domestic needs. China mainly produces rice, wheat, potatoes, onions, cabbage, beans, eggplant, spinach, carrots, cucumbers, tomatoes, pumpkins, pears, grapes, apples, peaches, plums, watermelons, sheep's milk, sheep, goats, chicken and pork, eggs, fish and honey products are produced. Although India is one of the largest producers of food in the world, its productivity is much lower than that of China, USA and Brazil. In addition, many citizens of India cannot afford to buy the food they produce.

Along with the use of innovative technologies, it is necessary to establish an effective management mechanism for production processes. In this case, it is necessary to use the organizational-economic mechanism of enterprise management, to apply optimal management methods based on methodological approaches.

The main reasons for the development of improved methods of organizational and economic mechanism of management in food industry enterprises of our country are:

- non-existence of a modern system related to solving the problem of food supply and related organizational and economic structure;
- lack of development of raw-finished product clusters in the field;
- failure to improve the quality control system of food products;
- the main reasons are the lack of development of an improved methodology for the implementation of conceptual rules for the efficient operation of economic entities and the regulation of food supply processes.

In order to increase the competitiveness of food industry enterprises, it is necessary to form the economic structure of the food supply system based on the integration of economic entities. This requires integration by bringing together functionally interdependent sectors, from agriculture to storage and delivery to the consumer.

This integration is developing widely in the textile industry of our country. Therefore, it is necessary to organize clusters in the food industry using the subsidies that are being formed in the textile industry.

The formation of such compounds in the industry is due to the development of the field of processing of agricultural products and the need to ensure the continuity of the stages of delivery of food products to consumers (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Process of integration of food industry enterprises

Integration serves as an important tool in ensuring the efficient operation of food industry enterprises, creating organizational and economic conditions, increasing the volume of food products, and organizing a continuous production process. It is especially important in the development of specialization in the production of agricultural products based on the characteristics of each region, in determining the standards of the products being produced.

In order to effectively organize the interaction of food industry enterprises with internal and external environmental factors, the organizational and economic mechanism developed should be based on several methodological approaches. In this mechanism, it is envisaged that the organizational coordination module will be managed by appropriate means based on the existing assessment criteria.

The creation of the mechanism consists of the process of choosing the most optimal of the types of integration, defining the boundaries of the structure, and distributing powers and functions (see Figure 2).

The functions of the mechanism are determined based on the level of synergy of each enterprise or association in the organizational structure, in which the private efficiency of economic entities is important. It is also envisaged to determine the factors affecting the efficiency with the help of a comprehensive evaluation of the mechanism and to provide the mechanism with optimal means.

Figure 2. Methodological aspects of the process of integration of food industry enterprises

Stages such as the merger, separation, and division of enterprises that take place during the integration process affect the change of the organizational and economic mechanism. Therefore, when developing an organizational-economic mechanism, it is first necessary to determine the exact structure of the enterprise, to evaluate its financial, organizational, and economic aspects.

Thus, the conceptual model of the organizational-economic management mechanism can be shown as follows (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Conceptual model of the organizational-economic mechanism of management

As mentioned above, the organizational-economic mechanism is a multifaceted concept that includes interrelated elements: principles, functions, methods, technologies. In this case, the principles of the organizational-economic mechanism determine the theoretical and practical basis of the functioning of the mechanism. Tasks represent the relations that arise in the process of management, the functions that must be performed in the manifestation of the characteristics of the organizational-economic mechanism. If style classifies a set of methods of influence on management processes, technology is an indirect reflection of methods and is a set of tools, processes and operations of management process implementation.

In the development of an effective organizational and economic mechanism for food industry enterprises, the role of the integration process is of great importance, it is possible to

create a set of mutually complementary cycles, to achieve the harmonization of processes from the cultivation of raw materials to the finished product. In addition, the resulting clusters serve to ensure competitiveness.

Therefore, it is recommended to establish large clusters in the food industry, link all stages from raw materials to finished products, improve the mechanism of product quality control, and develop diversification processes.

General conclusions on the topic.

1. The organizational-economic mechanism is a set of interrelated elements, which means the management process based on the combination of subjects, objects, principles, methods and other tools.

2. It is recommended to conditionally divide the factors affecting the organizational-economic mechanism of food industry enterprises into legal-regulatory, economic and organizational groups. As legal-regulatory factors, the changes caused by the improvement of the regulatory-legal framework have an effect, as economic factors, the change of tools such as price, tax, financing, insurance, credit, wages, and as organizational factors, the development of modern methods and methods of the management system have an effect. processes related to output are affected.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/100615/4-countries-producemostfood.asp#:~:text=Key%20Takeaways,for%20total%20geographic%20land%20area.>
2. Zdolnikova S.V. Organizational-economic mechanism of upravleniya innovatsionnym potensiam integrirovannyx promyshlennyx struktur. Nauchno-technicheskie vedomosti SPbGPU. Economic Science No. 4(246) 2016. p. 109-122. 116 p.